

ISic3349

Honorific inscription recording the colonia of Agrigentum

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2015.04.18

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Found 2008.06.25 during excavation of road parallel to decumanus maximus, bordering insula III; face-down in re-use in a late-antique tomb

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 37 cm

Width 55 cm

Depth 2.5 cm

Layout

Three lines of Latin text, centred on the surviving stone which is regularly cut but re-used

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letters are relatively tall, with marked serifs and an ornate interpunct on line 1. P is open with extended foot at base; R is closed; G is formed by single curved stroke

Letter heights:

Line 1: 60 mm

Line 2: 60-65 mm

Line 3: 65 mm

Interlineation

Line line1 to line1 : not measured mm

Text

1. col(oniae) · Septimiae ·

2. Aug(ustae) ·

3. Agrigentior(um)

Apparatus

Text after Silvestrini 2011

Translation (en)

of the colonia Septimia Augusta of the Agrigentines

Commentary

Probably from the front of a statue base. Silvestrini argues that the text should be understood to be in the genitive, and so dependent upon e.g. 'patrono' above. The context of erection in another city makes such identification plausible / explicable (while the absence, or potential absence of a dedicant is not in itself problematic). She further notes the Severan connection with the island, and the general current of African relations and trade in this period being of relevance for the Severans, before tracing significant families in this part of Sicily in this period as a plausible exempla of the sort of person / family likely to be honoured in this way. Silvestrini would restore: [- - - patrono] | col(oniae) Septimiae | Aug(ustae) | Agrigentior(um).

Digital identifiers:

TM 645593

EDCS 64100252

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3349. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358229>

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